

INDIVIDUALIZED HOMOEOPATHIC MEDICINE IN ANTI- THYROGLOBULIN ANTIBODY TITER IN HASHIMOTO THYROIDITIS- A CLINICAL STUDY

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Abstract

Hashimoto's thyroiditis is an autoimmune disease of the thyroid gland. It affects approximately 30-150 people per 100,000 people worldwide. A prospective single – arm clinical study without a control group was conducted on 30 cases chosen by purposive sampling from the Sarada Krishna homoeopathic medical college and hospital. The study included female patients aged 18 to 60 years with elevated thyroid stimulating hormone, anti- microsomal antibody/ anti-thyroid peroxidase antibody, and anti-thyroglobulin antibody. Patients with known cases of other autoimmune disorders, malignant thyroid cases, a state of hashitoxicosis, pregnant, post-partum, and lactating women were excluded from the study. Follow up assessment was done successively every month for the period of 12 months. All the parameters, namely anti-thyroglobulin-antibody, thyroid stimulating hormone, zulewski's clinical score, were improved in 18 cases. The wilcoxon signed rank test revealed a statistically significant result for the anti-thyroglobulin-antibody values of pre and post- test values, where the calculated value was found to be less than the tabled value and was significant at a p-value of 0.05. Thus, homoeopathic medicine was found to be effective in the reduction of anti-thyroglobulin-antibody levels.

Keywords: *Anti-thyroglobulin, Anti-Tg-Ab, Autoimmune thyroiditis, Hashimoto's Thyroiditis, Thyroid antibodies.*

INTRODUCTION

Hashimoto's thyroiditis (HT) is the autoimmune disease of the thyroid gland ^[1], which causes chronic inflammation and lymphocytic infiltration in the gland ^[2,3]. HT comes under the international classification of Disease code - ICD 10 E06.3 ^[4, 5]. Thyroid disorders affect approximately 42 million people in India ^[6], with HT being the most common in coastal areas where the iodine content of the diet is high ^[7, 8].

Thyroid-specific autoantibodies such as anti-thyroid peroxidase antibody (anti-TPO-Ab) and anti-thyroglobulin antibody (anti-Tg-Ab) were used to diagnose HT if they are present in high concentrations in the blood. The major-

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ity of HT cases exhibit hypothyroidism on thyroid function tests, with sub-clinical hypothyroidism being the most prevalent presentation, while some cases may present with euthyroidism or transient hyperthyroidism [2,9]. Clinical features are comparatively less in the initial stage of the disease, because the clinical manifestation occurs after the parenchymal damage of the thyroid gland. Yet both clinical and subclinical HT lead to various metabolic disorders [5].

The conventional medicine for hypothyroidism is the introduction of synthetic thyroid hormones [10], but the significant increase in incidence necessitates a new treatment [2, 6]. The aim of this study is to analyse the effectiveness of homoeopathic treatment and whether it could reduce the anti-Tg-Ab level in patients with Hashimoto's thyroiditis. Some previous studies on homoeopathic management of Hashimoto's thyroiditis showed a reduction in anti-TPO-Ab and anti-Tg-Ab titers [11-13].

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A prospective single-arm clinical study without a control group was conducted in out-patient department (OPD), in-patient department (IPD), thyroid specialty clinic and peripheral health center of Sarada Krishna Homoeopathic medical college (SKHMC). Duration of the study was from January 2021 to January 2022.

Selection of samples

Purposive sampling technique was used to select thirty cases.

Diagnostic criteria

Thyroid profile showing elevated TSH, anti- TPO- Ab, anti- Tg- Ab with low or normal tri-iodothyronine (T3) and thyroxine (T4).

Inclusion criteria

Female patients in 18 to 60 years of age with elevated TSH, Anti- TPO- Ab and Anti- Tg- Ab were included in this study.

Exclusion criteria

Pregnant, post-partum and lactating women. Known cases of other autoimmune disorders. Known malignant thyroid cases. Patients in state of Hashitoxicosis were excluded from the study.

Intervention

Homoeopathic medicine is selected with the help of the 'Homoeopathic medical repertory by Robin Murphy' according to the symptoms presented by the patient at the time of clinical interview. Homoeopathic medicines were administered in centesimal (C) or 50 millesimal (LM) potency. The repetition of medicine was according to the improvement of the patient. Follow up assessment- done successively every month for the period 12 months. Computer Repertorization tool 'Homopath Zomeo 2019 version' was used.

Statistical techniques

Pre and post-test values of anti- thyroglobulin antibodies were subjected to statistical test – wilcoxon signed rank test.

Data analysis

Data analysis was performed on the collected data using statistical computer software (Microsoft Excel).

Ethical approval

Institutional ethical committee Lr. No. EC/288/2021.

Outcome assessment

Based on anti-thyroglobulin antibody levels, TSH levels, zulewski's clinical score values of before and after 12 months of treatment. Outcome assessment criteria was based on the following categories, marked improvement in anti-tg-ab

reduction of more than 50 units. Moderate improvement in anti-Tg-Ab reduction of 20 to 50 units; mild improvement in anti-tg-ab reduction of 0- 20 units; if no improvement it means an increase in anti-Tg-Ab level.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The distribution of age shows that the maximum number of cases comes under the age group of 26–40 years old (53.3%) and 10 cases (33.3%) come under the age group of 18–25. A previous study conducted with the aim of describing the age and presentation of HT clinically showed the maximum of the cases fell under the age group of 21–30, and the second most common age group reported was 31–40 [14]. The age range of 26 to 40 years saw the highest number of instances reported in my study as well.

According to the survey study named the Pescopagano survey, conducted in Italy over a study duration of 15 years, concluded that excessive dietary iodine showed a 4 times higher prevalence rate of HT than in iodine deficient areas [15]. Another study suggested that the excess iodine intake might cause the negative feedback mechanism, which in turn becomes the causative factor for hypothyroidism [16]. Similarly, in my study, 29 cases (50.88%) out of 30 cases had the risk factor of residing in the iodine sufficient area, i.e., having their residence within 20 km of the sea shore. Another similar finding that the thyroid disorders were prevalent in coastal areas, and one litre of sea water contains 0.05 mg of iodine, which is also present in the same proportion in sea fish. Thus, in my study also, the geographical features and food habits in the coastal region account for its higher incidence of HT [17].

Among 30 cases, when compared with the anti-Tg-Ab level in pre and post- test, the highest difference was shown in the pre- test value of 4000 IU/ml, which was reduced to 128 IU/ml with a difference of 3872 IU/ml. In 12 cases, there was a significant improvement of more than 50 units. In four cases, there was a moderate improvement in the reduction of anti-Tg-Ab levels of 20 to 50 units. Mild improvement of a reduction in anti-Tg-Ab level of 0-20 units was seen in 3 cases. When comparing before and after treatment values of anti-Tg-Ab level by the Wilcoxon signed rank test method, and a calculated p-value less than the tabled value at 0.05. This shows that the result was statistically significant. A similar study showed the pre-test anti-Tg-Ab value of 480 IU/ml (ECIA) was reduced to 1.6 IU/ml (CLIA). It concluded that individualised homoeopathy is effective in controlling the antibody level in Hashimoto's thyroiditis [11]. The reduction in anti-Tg-Ab in my study is in accordance with the above-mentioned case report (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Distribution of cases according to anti-Tg-Ab level in comparison with pre and post- test values

As reported in Fig. 2, all the patients showed reduction in TSH level. This result is in accordance with another study where 76 patients showed a complete drop in TSH levels with no additional increases in TSH levels, 84 cases showed

a significant reduction in TSH levels out of 200 cases [19]. Another study also showed a similar result in the reduction of TSH level with homoeopathic medicine [20]. Thus, the improvement in the TSH level reported in my study is in accordance with the studies mentioned above.

Fig. 2. Distribution of cases according to TSH level in comparison with pre and post- test values

In zulewski’s clinical score was reduced in all the cases. Another study suggests that the zulewski score reduces in relation to the reduction in TSH level [18]. In my study too, the reduction of zulewski’s score is in correlation with the reduction in TSH level.

In my study, among three parameters used in the assessment of HT (Fig. 3), the most marked improvement was shown in the parameter Anti-Tg-Ab, with 12 out of 30 cases; next to it, TSH showed moderate improvement in 12 out of 30 cases; and lastly, by assessing the clinical score of Zulewski, which showed moderate improvement in 15 out of 30 cases. In a similar study TSH level and zulewski’s score were both reduced [21]. In another similar study, the TSH level and thyroid specific auto-antibody levels were reduced in comparison with the control group[13]. Thus, the post-test improvement in the three parameters (TSH, zulewski’s score, and antibody titer) was in accordance with the previous research studies in homoeopathy.

Fig. 3. Distribution of cases according to improvement in comparison with Anti-Tg-Ab, TSH, Zulewski’s score

The Homoeopathic medical repertory by Robin Murphy was used to select the indicated medicine among the 30 cases (Table. 1). Natrum muriaticum was indicated in 11 cases (36.37%). This is in accordance with the similar studies, natrum muriaticum was found effective in reducing the TSH levels [6, 22]. Thus, the most frequently indicated remedy, 'natrum muriaticum' in my study is in accordance with the previous studies in thyroid disorders managed with homoeopathic medicine.

Table 1. Distribution of cases according to remedy prescribed

Medicine	No of cases	Percentage
Nat mur	11	36.67%
Calc iod	6	20.00%
Calc carb	5	16.67%
Arum met	1	3.33%
Iodum	1	3.33%
Lach	1	3.33%
Lyco	1	3.33%
Phos	1	3.33%
Pulsatilla	1	3.33%
Sep	1	3.33%
Staph	1	3.33%

The potency is selected according to the susceptibility of the patient. The most commonly used potencies in this study were 200 C in the majority of the cases, with a frequency of 12, and the percentage was 40%. Next, 0/1 was given to 8 patients with a 26.67%. In 4 cases, 30 C was given (41.33%), 1M was given to 4 cases (13.33%), and in 2 cases, 0/3 was given (6.67%). The majority of the cases were prescribed with 200 C, which is in accordance with the previous study where 200 C was used in the maximum of the prescriptions and then 1M (1000 C) potency was used next in frequency [11]. Thus, in my study also, the frequently indicated potency was 200 C, which is in accordance with the previous research study.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that homoeopathic individualised medicine shows a positive effect in reducing the level of anti-Tg-Ab, TSH, and Zulewski score in Hashimoto's thyroiditis. In further studies, longer study durations and rigorous study designs are required to confirm the results.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

No conflict of interest.

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